

ON LINE OPTIMISATION AND ACTIVE CONTROL OF THE CURE PROCESS OF THICK COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an active control scheme for the cure of advanced composites based on the combination of simulation with cure monitoring signals. The cure of composites is a time-intensive and energy-consuming process, often carried out under conservative conditions to satisfy process performance metrics and deal with variability. Utilisation of process simulation alongside online signals presents an opportunity to increase process efficiency, while also ensuring process robustness. An accurate cure simulation model is developed here based on detailed constitutive models, taking into consideration cure kinetics as well as the evolution of thermal properties during the cure. The development of a dielectric sensor compatible with carbon fibre reinforcement and a protocol for its calibration achieves direct and accurate measurement of the degree of cure in the curing component. This, accompanied by thermal monitoring signals, informs the simulation to predict the level of temperature overshoot online, taking into account the process history and the current state of the part. Incorporation of this information in an active control loop permits updating the thermal profile to minimise process duration, while ensuring temperature overshoot is kept below a limit. Implementation of the strategy in the curing of thick carbon fibre cable achieves a process time reduction of about 65%, demonstrating the clear cost and energy consumption benefits of the approach developed.

1 INTRODUCTION

The cure of thermosetting matrix fibre composites is a crucial stage of the manufacturing chain that plays a major role in component quality and overall manufacturing cost. In designing the cure process, manufacturers need to address often competing objectives of minimising process time, minimising tooling cost, ensuring temperature uniformity, and minimising exothermic effects, whilst satisfying constraints of adherence to process certification requirements and addressing variability challenges. Current industrial approaches address the overall problem by adopting conservative thermal profiles, usually comprising two or more isothermal segments, resulting in expensive and energy-consuming manufacturing, adversely affecting both part cost and overall sustainability.

The inefficiency of cure processing becomes more pronounced in thick parts. The exothermic character of the cure reaction, combined with the low thermal conductivity of curing composites in the thickness direction, makes temperature overshoots likely, forcing manufacturers to adopt even more conservative thermal profiles, often involving an initial long isothermal segment at low temperature to consume a significant part of the matrix reactivity under mild conditions. This increases the cost of processing significantly, often making the adoption of a composite solution for thick parts uneconomical.

Numerical optimisation methods have been put forward as a potential solution for addressing cure cost minimisation and maximisation of product quality. Optimisation approaches integrate, in their core, a method for mapping process variables (e.g., thermal profile variables, tooling properties, environmental variables) into process outcomes (maximum overshoot, process duration, cure uniformity, thermal gradients) through simulation [1] or data-based representations combined with models [2]. Optimisation schemes, such as gradient-based techniques [3], genetic algorithms [4], and neural networks [5, 6], are used to identify optimal process conditions and setups that can minimise process duration or cost, maximise quality/minimise defects, or achieve both in a multi-objective setting.

Numerical optimisation exploits regions of high sensitivity of the objectives to the design variables, often obtaining solutions that have a level of instability. In practical terms, this means processing carried out under optimal conditions can be potentially affected more by variability in the manufacturing environment and materials. The process of cure is subject to uncertainty due to variability in surface heat transfer coefficients, ambient conditions in the manufacturing environment, and the initial state of the curing matrix material [7, 8]. The utilisation of process monitoring provides a solution for resolving the uncertainty associated with composite manufacturing, with techniques based on optical, electric/dielectric, and ultrasonic sensing [9 -13] offering solutions for both the flow and cure stages of processing. In a recent development, temperature monitoring has been combined with modelling of the cure of carbon fibre composites to achieve online optimisation in an active control scheme, delivering significant simultaneous reduction in cure duration and temperature overshoot, with improvements matching those achieved using numerical optimisation, and without being affected by issues related to uncertainty [14].

The present work extends active control of cure with the utilisation of dielectric cure sensors. The method involves models for translating dielectric signals to an online estimation of degree of cure. This, alongside thermal signals and simulation of cure and its associated constitutive models, is used to predict an optimal temperature setting dynamically as the process evolves. The control scheme developed is applied to the cure of a thick carbon fibre cable to validate the development.

2 METHODS

2.1 Material characterisation

The material used is unidirectional (UD) carbon fibres prepreg with 12K tows and areal density of 385 g/m² with an epoxy resin mixed with hardener and accelerator (System A). The cured ply thickness of the prepreg is 0.358 mm.

Cure kinetics was characterised using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) experiments in a DSC 250 Discovery (TA Instruments). Isothermal cure tests were carried at 120 and 110°C, following a 10°C/min ramp from ambient to the test temperature and then holding until completion of the reaction. Dynamic cure tests were performed at 2 and 10°C/min from ambient temperature to reaction completion. Isothermal heat flow signals were integrated using a horizontal baseline to calculate the degree of cure and its evolution. Integration of dynamic signals was carried out using a sigmoidal baseline. The fitting of the cure kinetics model to the experimental data to determine the values of cure kinetics parameters was performed using Solver of Microsoft Excel [15]. The evolution of the glass transition temperature as a function of the degree of was investigated using 10 samples partially cured from fully unreacted to complete reaction at 2 °C/min. The glass transition temperature of these samples was measured using the inflection point of the heat flow step at the transition in dynamic DSC tests at 10°C /min.

The evolution of specific heat capacity during the cure was measured using the DSC 250 Discovery (TA Instruments) in modulation mode. Two isothermal tests were carried out at 130 and 110°C and one dynamic at 1°C/min. In all experiments, a modulation amplitude of 1°C and modulation period of 60 s were used. Thermal conductivity in the thickness and fibre directions was measured using a Laser Flash Analyser (TA Instruments LFA Discovery 1200). Cured samples of the prepreg comprising 4 plies and 50 plies were utilised for the through thickness and fibre direction measurements. The specimen size was 10 mm × 10 mm in both cases. Prior to the measurement the specimens were sprayed with graphite to enhance optical absorption. A laser power of 1200 W was used, and measurements comprising 3 laser shots were performed in the temperature range of 20-160 °C at 40 °C intervals. The parameters of the

corresponding constitutive models for specific heat capacity and thermal conductivity through fitting to the experimental data using Solver of Microsoft Excel [15].

2.2 Manufacturing trials and process monitoring setup

A round cable with length of 2.8m consisting of wound UD prepreg plies, equivalent to 115 layers from centre to the surface consolidated by release film resulting in a diameter of 41 mm for the whole assembly was cured in an industrial oven. Two K-type thermocouples and two dielectric sensors were placed on the outer surface and in the centre of the cable. The setup of the experiment is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Trial setup: (left) wound cable with sensors and connectors; (right) curing setup.

The dielectric sensor used in the experiments is based on twisted insulated copper wires [13], which was weaved into a glass fibre cloth (Figure 2). Data acquisition for both dielectric sensors and thermocouples was carried out using a DETA-SCOPE from ADVISE-DETA [16]. Dielectric measurements were acquired in the frequency range of 1 Hz to 20 kHz. The capacitance (C) at 10 Hz was utilised to determine the degree of cure. Calibration experiments were carried out off-line using a thermal profile comprising isothermal segments at 110 and 150°C and 1°C/min ramps. Temperature signals were acquired and the cure kinetics model for the material of the study was used to calculate degree of cure (α) values to determine the coefficients b , c , and d of the calibration function:

$$\alpha = b + c \log C + \frac{d}{T} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: Sensor setup: (left) detail of sensing wire; (right) integration in woven cloth.

2.3 Cure simulation

Cure simulation was carried out using the Finite Element (FE) solver FLEXPDP 7 [17]. The solver allows the definition of non-linear constitutive models coupled with differential equations. The problem

solved corresponds to the representation of the cure of a circular cross-section cable in cylindrical coordinates expressed as:

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(K \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) = \rho c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - (1 - v_f) \rho_r H_{tot} \frac{d\alpha}{dt}, \quad r \in [0, R_{cable}] \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the density of the composite, c_p is its specific heat capacity, T the temperature, α the degree of cure, K the thermal conductivity in the radial direction, v_f the fibre volume fraction, ρ_r the resin density, H_{tot} the total heat of the curing reaction, and R_{cable} the radius of the cable. The reaction rate is expressed as:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{A_1 e^{-E_1/RT} (1 - \alpha)^{n_1} + A_2 e^{-E_2/RT} \alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^{n_2}}{1 + e^{C_0[a - a_c - a_T T]}} \quad (3)$$

Here where m , n_1 and n_2 are reaction orders, A_1 and A_2 are pre-exponential factors, E_1 and E_2 are activation energies and R is the universal gas constant. The denominator of Eq. 2 incorporates diffusion limitations in the cure kinetics model through a critical value of the degree of cure expressed as a function of temperature, where a_T , a_c are phenomenological parameters controlling the value of critical degree of cure as a function of temperature, and C_0 is a parameter controlling the breadth of the transition to diffusion-control. The specific heat capacity is a function of the degree of cure and temperature, implemented through the dependence of the instantaneous glass transition temperature on the degree of cure, expressed by:

$$c_p = A + \alpha G + \frac{B}{1 + e^{C_1(T_g - T + F)}} + T \left(D + \frac{H}{1 + e^{C_1(T_g - T + F)}} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$T_g = T_{g0} + \frac{\lambda \alpha (T_{g\infty} - T_{g0})}{1 - (1 - \lambda) \alpha} \quad (5)$$

where A , B , D , F , G and H are fitting coefficients, C_1 is a parameter controlling the breadth of the glass transition, T_{g0} and $T_{g\infty}$ are the glass transition temperatures of the uncured and fully cured material respectively and λ is a parameter controlling the convexity of the dependence of glass transition temperature on degree of cure. The thermal conductivity of the composite material is considered to be a linear function of temperature, with the corresponding constitutive model accounting for different conductivities in the fibre and transverse or thickness direction. In the case of the one-dimensional model of the cable, only the transverse conductivity is utilised in the solution.

Assuming uniform heating across around the cable, the heat transfer problem becomes one-dimensional in the radial direction. Symmetry implies a perfect insulation boundary condition at the cable centre. The nominal thermal profile was applied as a prescribed temperature boundary condition on the outer surface. Initial conditions are imposed at every model run following the monitored values of temperature and degree of cure at the model start, with an assumed distribution across the radial direction.

2.4 Active control scheme

The active control strategy reported in [14] was extended to incorporate cure monitoring data. A representation of the active control scheme is shown in Figure 3. The active control tool aims to determine in real time instantaneous temperatures that do not produce a high temperature overshoot while minimising the duration of the cure of the process. This is achieved by executing the simulation at every increment using existing monitoring data to define updated initial conditions.

The control system suggests a cure temperature higher than the current setpoint value, whilst considering the measured temperature and degree of cure on the cable surface and core as initial conditions in the cure simulation. The control system accepts the suggested temperature if - based on the results of the simulation - it does not produce an overshoot exceeding a predefined limit (set at 10°C here) before cure completion (Figure 4-left). If the new temperature is rejected, due to an unacceptably high overshoot (Figure 4-right), the suggested temperature is maintained at the current level and the

simulation is rerun to determine if the current temperature is acceptable. If the condition of overshoot below the limit is adhered to the temperature is maintained otherwise the temperature is lowered.

Figure 3: Integrated monitoring – modelling – control setup.

Figure 4: Examples of active control scenarios: (left) accepted increment in temperature as overshoot limit is not exceeded; (right) rejected increment due to overshoot greater than the limit occurring prior to cure completion.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Constitutive models

Figure 5 illustrates the performed fitting of the cure kinetics model of Eq. 3. The model follows both dynamic and isothermal data closely with an average absolute error of $1.5E-5$ for isothermal tests and $2.0E-4$ for dynamic tests. The model reproduces successfully the autocatalytic character of the reaction at low degrees of cure and the dominance of nth reaction kinetics at high degrees of cure. The Di Benedetto equation fitting (Eq.5) matches experimental data closely with an average absolute error of $2.5^{\circ}C$. The fitting of Eq.4 to specific heat capacity data is presented in Figure 6-left. The model reproduces experimental data successfully including the transition region. The average error in specific heat capacity values is $0.006 J/g/^{\circ}C$. The linear fitting of thermal conductivity data is illustrated in Figure 6-right. As expected, the conductivity in the fibre direction is significantly greater than in the thickness/transverse direction. Overall, the constitutive models map well the evolution of properties and of reaction rate as a function of temperature and degree of cure, which provides the basis for an accurate heat transfer model of the cure.

Figure 5: Cure kinetics model: (left) isothermal cure; (right) dynamic cure.

Figure 6: Constitutive models: (left) specific heat capacity; (right) thermal conductivity.

3.2 On line monitoring of the degree of cure

Figure 7 illustrates the accuracy of the use of Eq.1 for the determination of the degree of cure based on data of capacitance obtained by the dielectric sensing setup. The degree of cure based on the kinetics model reaches about 70% at the end of the first isothermal segment, progresses to about 90% at the end of the ramp, and reaches its maximum value of about 98% after 40 min at the high temperature isothermal segment. The fitting is accurate with some small deviations in the early stages of cure. The sensing data and calibration equation provide a very good direct estimate of the degree of cure even under non-isothermal conditions or when the conditions are nominally isothermal but there is significant deviation in temperature with time. The robustness of the degree of cure estimation is key for enabling its use in an active control loop.

Figure 7: Validation of cure sensing functionality.

3.3 Active control trial

The results of the active control trial are illustrated in Figure 8. The degree of cure from the sensors is provided to the active control every 60 s. The initial temperature is 70°C, and the process is held at this temperature until the temperature sensors in the part approach 60°C. At this point, the active control algorithm starts increase the temperature gradually as predicted overshoots are well below the limit. This results in effective heating rate of about 1°C/min, translated to a lower but broadly uniform heating rate in the curing part. The prediction of overshoot becomes greater than the limit of 10°C when the part reaches about 90°C and the oven temperature is about 105°C. The oven temperature is stabilised at that level for about 60 min. After that time, the temperature in the part exceeds 100°C and the degree of cure reaches about 30%. At this point it is possible to increase the temperature without inducing an unacceptable overshoot, as a significant part of the reactivity of the resin has been consumed. The active control algorithm increases the temperature gradually at an average rate that approximates 1°C/min, up to about 150°C. The composite part follows at a similar rate as a result of the exothermicity of the reaction which progresses by about 50%. This is indicative of the capability of the active control system to use the heat of the curing reaction to benefit the efficiency of the process. A further 40 min at 150°C is required to complete the cure, after which colling down starts.

During the whole process, the temperature in the part is relatively uniform, with gradients kept below 10°C. The maximum overshoot observed is only 3.5°C occurring right after reaching the second isothermal segment of the profile. This shows the efficiency of the control, as the ramp stops just before an overshoot is manifested, ensuring the positive feedback of reaction exothermicity does not dominate the evolution of the thermal profile. The role of accurate sensing in this is paramount, as the strong non-linearity of exothermic effects would have easily created a risk if similar decisions for the oven temperature profile have been taken without accurate information of the state and temperature of the curing part. The degree of cure evolution is relatively uniform across the radius of the cable, with the different parts reaching the same level of cure within 10 min. The total cure time using the active control system is 2.6 h. This, compared to the 7 h duration of the nominal cure profile for the material used, represents an improvement of about 65%. This significant reduction is reflected in a corresponding improvement in both process costs and emissions. These are achieved whilst ensuring that part quality is equivalent to that obtained with the use of a conventional, slow cure profile.

Figure 8: Demonstration of active control operation in curing of UD carbon fibre cable.

4 CONCLUSIONS

An active control strategy based on use of cure monitoring signals alongside simulation has been developed and implemented in this work. The demonstration of the system in the cure of a thick carbon fibre cable shows that the ability to inform the control algorithm with accurate thermal and cure signals allows the process to exploit the exothermicity of the curing reaction in a controlled manner. Achieving reduction in cure time by about 65%, whilst maintaining temperature uniformity and ensuring associated quality metrics are met, presents a major opportunity for decreasing costs and energy usage. This enhances the overall sustainability of composites.

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